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A Comparative Evaluation of Undergraduate Programs of Arabic Translation and Interpreting Departments in Turkey

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Abstract

It is seen that the importance and need for Arabic have been increasing in Turkey in recent years, and the variety and number of programs for the Arabic language in higher education institutions are also increasing. It is noteworthy that the Arabic Language and Literature and Arabic Language Teaching departments, which have a long history, and the Arabic Translation and Interpretation departments, have been increasing in the state and private universities in recent years. In this study, the undergraduate programs of the Arabic translation and interpretation departments in the first three universities, which currently accept students from state universities, were examined from various perspectives. In these universities, the number of courses of Arabic Translation and Interpretation departments, the courses and the intensity of the translation field according to the semesters were evaluated. As a result of the study, it draws attention that there are differences between the programs. The differences observed in the undergraduate programs of these departments, which were opened for the same purpose, suggest that a common program should be created between the departments. In this context, some suggestions have been made regarding the current status of Arabic translation and interpretation undergraduate programs at universities.

Keywords: Education planning, Program, Higher education, Translation and interpretation, Translation education, Arabic

1. Introduction

In recent years, remarkably important steps have been taken regarding the teaching of Arabic in Turkey. Depending on Turkey's geographical location and history, its relationship with Arabic speaking countries increases the importance of this language. Arabic is among the most desired foreign languages to be learned as a foreign language after English among Turkish society. The fact that Arabic, which is among the official languages

accepted by the UN, is included under the name of various programs in higher education institutions makes it necessary to examine this field.

In order for the manpower developed in the education process to reach the determined target it is necessary to have a planned education program in this process. It has become necessary for the education system to train manpower in quality and quantity equipped with the knowledge and skills appropriate to the contemporary developments required by the development at all levels and fields (Tok, 2006, p.1). It is an educational program that is a guide that handles the educational process in every aspect, plans it and determines what will be done according to the objectives to be achieved. The education program, which is one of the building blocks of the education process, has a different importance at all levels. The curriculum is the planned arrangement of the knowledge, skills, attitudes, behaviors that are desired to be acquired by the student in line with the objectives of the education program. Thus, this program, which includes in-school life, is a guide that covers the lessons taught (Komisyon, 2010, p. 33; akt. Özcan, 2012, p.12). The perspective of the curriculum is generally expressed by the Ministry of National Education as follows:

“The main purpose of our education system is to raise individuals with knowledge, skills and behaviors integrated with values and competencies. While trying to gain knowledge, skills and behaviors through curricula, our values and competencies function as a link and horizon that establishes the integrity between these knowledge, skills and behaviors (MEB, 2019, p. 4).”

Translation education can be defined as giving theoretical and practical courses in order to gain the ability of translating between languages to individuals who receive any foreign language education. A foreign language learner can produce qualified translations from a foreign language to the mother tongue or among the foreign languages he has learned, thanks to the lessons he has taken in this field. Güngenci and Yıldız (2020, p.706) state that besides the four basic skills of listening, speaking, reading and writing, translation activity can also be seen as a language skill. Graduates of translation and interpreting departments, where translation education is given, can perform translation as a profession.

The translation profession is a profession in itself that provides written-oral communication between two different languages and cultures at every stage of international relations, and requires specialization and professionalism in itself according to the application areas (İletişim Başkanlığı, 2021, p.14). Accordingly, the courses that will enable candidates of the profession in the departments of translation and interpreting to translate in various fields during their education and provide them with expertise should be included in the education program. In this process, the education programs that form the framework of the basic knowledge and skills that students are expected to acquire in a specific field are important. Akalın (2016, s.57), emphasizes that it is necessary to determine the requirements, criteria, criteria and common acceptances in education by defending that translation training institutions are based on chance and that it is impossible for a translator to earn her life by chance. Evaluation is an indispensable tool for meeting needs or filling identified gaps, correcting errors, reorganizing and updating the program (Bantwini, 2010). Examining any undergraduate program or an education program at a different level in the light of certain criteria will provide an opportunity to update the deficiencies or differences in that program.

According to Varış (1988), education program development in education cannot be solved by being limited within the framework of certain people's own ideas. In order to ensure the development of the educational process, it is necessary to go to the source of the problem, to examine the success of students and teachers in the school, and to observe the functioning of the school. In order to get an absolute conclusion about the strengths and weaknesses of the program, it may be necessary to evaluate it with various variables states that the Taba-Tyler approach is focused on the program development process in Turkey (Demirel 1992, p. 32). It is recommended to work in eight stages in the process followed according to this approach. These stages are listed as follows: Determining the needs, determining the goals, selecting the content, organizing the content, choosing the learning experiences, organizing the learning activities, determining what to evaluate, the order of the program elements and the control of the relationships (Oliva, 1988, p.165).

In this study, by analyzing the curriculum of the Arabic translation and interpreting departments, it was revealed which courses were focused on during the education. Accordingly, it was examined that which courses of the curriculum of the undergraduate program with the same name in different universities differ from each other.

1.1. Current Situation in Arabic Translation and Interpreting Departments in Turkey

Translation, which plays an important role in intercultural interaction, increases its importance day by day with the increase of inter-country communication. Accordingly, translation departments are opened in higher education institutions in order to train qualified manpower. Of course, the need for translation and translators is on the rise due to the peak of Turkey's international relations in economic, political, cultural and touristic fields for the last 30-35 years, especially in the last 15 years (Ersoy, Şahin ve Türkmen. 2017, p.414). The beginning of translation education in higher education in Turkey dates back to 1980s. Firstly, in the academic year of 1983-1984, Boğaziçi and Hacettepe universities started translation education with English translation and interpreting departments. (Eruz, 2003, p.96). In the beginning of the 90's, translation training in French and German languages besides English started in Turkey (Bildik, 2015, p.70). Today, besides the languages listed, there are translation and interpretation departments of Arabic, Bulgarian, Chinese, Persian and Russian languages. (YÖK, 2020). According to the report published by the Republic of Turkey Prime Ministry Administration Development Presidency on the translation profession in 2015, translation education in our country is in English (54%), French (17%), German (11%), Russian (7%), Arabic (6%) and other languages (5%). (Bulgarian, Chinese, Kyrgyz) (Başbakanlık İdareyi Geliştirme Başkanlığı, 2015, p. 17).

Considering the developing relations between Arab countries and Turkey in recent years, Arabic translation-interpretation departments have been established in order to meet the need for translators by training qualified translators in the field of Arabic-Turkish translation. Both oral and written Arabic Turkish translation training is provided in the Arabic translation and interpretation departments, which have been established and started to operate within both private universities and government universities. Accordingly, it is important to examine the undergraduate curricula that provide information about the translation education provided in these departments. Suçin (2015, p.41-51), In his presentation titled "Arabic translation training and Arabic literary translation workshops in Turkey" he presented in the Young Interpreters Workshop, he made some suggestions about translation education by evaluating the Arabic translation education in the existing departments related to Arabic in Turkey. Kara (2010, s.99), emphasizes that the translation education given in the academic environment has important duties by evaluating the translators who are well-equipped, experts in their fields and who have absorbed the knowledge of translational methodology as one of the cornerstones of today's language and intercultural communication network. Especially, it is an important point that translator candidates, who have an important place in this field, work on practice besides their theoretical knowledge and as a result they reach a qualified position in their field. The main purpose of institutions that provide translation education should be to train translators who can achieve the academic development and progress of translation, within the framework of industrializing world conditions, by combining the theoretical and practical aspects of translation, and who can meet the professional requirements in the translation sector (Erol, 2017, p.83).

In addition to Arabic language and literature, Arabic teaching departments, Arabic translation and interpretation departments have also increased quantitatively in recent years. One of the primary reasons for this is the need for educated manpower in this field depending on the relations between countries. The status of undergraduate programs related to Arabic that are currently enrolling students at universities in Turkey is as follows:

Table 1: Distribution of Programs

Program Name	Government University	Private University	Total
Arabic Language Teaching	4	4	8
Arapça Language and Literature	9	-	9
Translation and Interpretation (Arabic) Faculty	3	2	4
Translation and Interpretation (Arabic) College	1	2	4

(YÖK, 2020)

Table 1 shows that there are three different undergraduate programs related to Arabic in universities. It is seen that the department of Arabic language and literature is more than the other departments in terms of quantity. Some of the Translation and Interpreting departments are within the faculty, while others continue their education in the colleges of universities. There is no difference between the departments in the college and the programs in the faculty. It is noteworthy that Arabic teaching and translation and interpreting departments have an equal distribution among both state and private universities. However, it is striking that the department of Arabic language and literature is not available at private universities. A total of eight Arabic translation and interpreting departments are active, four in foundation universities and four in state universities. These departments aim to train translators with sufficient professional knowledge and equipment in the field of Arabic-Turkish translation. In this study, the curricula of the first three Arabic Translation and Interpretation departments, which were established within government universities and started education, were compared. Among these departments, Kırıkkale University Arabic Translation and Interpretation undergraduate program was established in 2011 and started teaching in the 2011-2012 academic year. The Arabic translation-interpretation department at this university was previously the department of Arabic language and literature, and it is the first department to be opened among state universities in this field. In the 2014-2015 academic year, 250 students receive education in the department, which gave its first graduates. Kırıkkale University Faculty of Arts and Sciences Arabic Translation and Interpretation Department has 50 quotas and accepts students in the type of language score. (Kırıkkale Üniversitesi, 2020). Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey University Arabic Translation and Interpretation Department was established in 2017 within the School of Foreign Languages and started its educational activities in the 2018-2019 academic year. The department, which receives 60 students per year from the language score type, continues its education with 180 students. The third Department of Arabic Translation and Interpretation included in this study was established within Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences and started education in the 2017-2018 academic year. The department, which accepts students from the language score type, accepts 60 students per year. All these departments, which provide one-year preparatory education, provide five years of education, including preparatory + 4 (four) years undergraduate.

2. Method

2.1. Aim of Study

The aim of the research is to create a framework for the current education programs of Arabic translation and interpreting departments in higher education institutions. Thus, it was aimed to reveal the differences and similarities of this developing department. In addition, various suggestions were made by revealing the differences between these departments.

2.2. Limitations of the Study

In the research, Arabic Translation and Interpretation departments programs in higher education institutions were discussed to analyze documents. Undergraduate curriculum of the programs has been examined and based on field courses. Preparatory education and elective courses are excluded from the research. This research was limited to examine the number of courses and the items of course content in order to determine the differences and similarities between the programs. In addition, this study covers the first three universities opened in state universities and the departments that currently accept students. The program of the same department in private universities is not covered in this study.

2.3. Universe and Sample

The universe of the research consists of Arabic Translation and Interpretation Undergraduate programs that provide education in higher education institutions. The sample of the study consists of the first three undergraduate programs opened in state universities as the department of Arabic Translation and Interpretation. These universities: Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University, Kırıkkale University and Karamanoglu Mehmetbey University.

2.4. Method of Research

Document analysis method that is one of the qualitative research methods was used in the study. Document analysis is a qualitative research method used to diligently and systematically analyze the content of documents. Document analysis is a systematic method used to examine and evaluate all documents, including printed and electronic materials. Like other methods used in qualitative research, document analysis requires the analysis and interpretation of data in order to make sense, create an understanding about the relevant subject, and develop empirical knowledge (Corbin & Strauss, 2008). The programs utilized by this method in this research were evaluated under various factors.

3. Findings

3.1. Number of Courses

The table below offers the opportunity to compare the number of undergraduate courses in Arabic Translation and Interpretation departments at universities in Turkey. In this table, the current curriculum shared by universities on their websites is discussed. The number of courses is indicated without making the distinction between elective and compulsory courses. In this table, YOK compulsory 5-i courses are not included in the number of courses. There is number of courses on Arabic translation education.

Table 2: Arabic Translation and Interpreting Departments Distribution of Arabic Translation Courses

	Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University	Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey University	Kırıkkale University
1st Semester	7	5	5
2nd Semester	8	5	5
3rd Semester	11	7	7
4th Semester	11	7	7
5th Semester	9	8	8
6th Semester	9	8	8
7th Semester	9	7	8
8th Semester	7	7	8
Total	71	54	56

Although the number of courses of KKMU and KKMU Arabic Translation and Interpreting departments is close to each other during their education, the number of courses AYBU Arabic Translation and Interpreting Department is higher than other departments. This situation brings an intense course load at AYBU during undergraduate education compared to other universities.

Table 3: Rate of Translation Courses in Programs Over Other Courses According to Universities

Program Areas	AYBU	Kırıkkale University	Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey University
Translation Courses	%40,2	%37,1	%41,6
Other Courses	%59,8	%62,9	%58,4
Total	%100	%100	%100

When the distribution of "translation courses" and "other courses" of the programs according to universities is examined, it is seen that the rates of Arabic teaching, elective courses and 5i (English, History, Turkish Language etc.) courses are higher than translation courses. However, the rates of translation courses vary between programs. Translation courses are offered at the rate of 40.2% in AYBU, 37.1% in KKMU and 41.6% in KKMU. In this case, it has been determined that the number of translation courses of the KKMU Arabic Translation and Interpreting

Department undergraduate program is higher than the other departments. AYBU and KKU programs follow this section, respectively.

3.2. Courses in The Arabic Translation and Interpreting Departments

Table 4: 1st Semester Field Information Course Distribution

No	Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University	Kırıkkale University	Karamanoglu Mehmetbey University
1.	Grammar I	Arabic Grammar I	Arabic Grammar I
2.	Writing Skill I	Dictation	Written Expression I
3.	Oral Expression I	Oral Communication I	Oral Communication I
4.	Pre-Islamic Arab Culture	Lexicology I	Lexicology I
5.	Reading-Analysis I	Reading Translation I	Introduction to Translation I
6.	Legal Translation I (Arabic-Turkish)	-	-
7.	Media Translation	-	-

When the first semester courses of Arabic Translation and Interpreting Undergraduate programs are examined, it is seen that there are similar courses on language skills in all departments. However, there are also differences between the programs. While AYBU has seven courses in the first term, it is seen that there are five courses in KKU and KMU. In terms of translation courses, "Legal Translation I (Arabic-Turkish)" and "Media Translation" courses at AYBU, "Reading Translation-I" course at KKU and "Introduction to Translation I" course at KMU are in the program. When a comparison is made in terms of translation courses, it is seen that translation specialization courses are given starting from the first semester in AYBU program. The reason for this may be the thought that students who take preparatory education have completed a certain amount of language skills lessons.

Table 5: 2nd Semester Field Information Course Distribution

No	Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University	Kırıkkale University	Karamanoglu Mehmetbey University
1.	Grammar II	Arabic Grammar II	Arabic Grammar II
2.	Auditory Analysis	Lexicology II	Lexicology II
3.	Writing Skill II	Written Expression I	Written Expression II
4.	Oral Expression II	Oral Communication II	Oral Communication II
5.	Reading-Analysis II	Reading Translation II	Introduction to Translation II
6.	News Translation I (Arabic-Turkish)	-	-
7.	Legal Translation II (Turkish-Arabic)	-	-
8.	Post-Islamic Arab Culture I (Islamic period and Umayyads)	-	-

When second semester courses are examined, it is seen that language skills courses are available in this period and that the first term courses are continuation in all three programs. When the programs are evaluated in terms of translation courses, it is seen that the "Legal Translation I" course is given with translation from Arabic to Turkish in the first semester in the AYBU program, there is "Legal Translation II" course is a continuation course with translation from Turkish to Arabic in the second semester. In addition, as in the first semester, there is a lesson on Arab culture in this semester as a lesson on "Post-Islamic Arab Culture I (Islamic period and Umayyads) at AYBU. Besides that, instead of the "Media Translation" course in the first semester, "News Translation I (Arabic-Turkish)" is taught in the second semester. As can be seen, many courses in this semester are the continuation of the previous term courses.

Language skills courses in the KKU program are a continuation of the previous term and it is seen that the "Written Expression I" course is included instead of the "Dictation" course. In this department program, it is seen that the students are aimed to be competent in Arabic writing and to improve their dictation skills, and then to improve

their written expression skills with the written expression course. There is a "Reading Translation II" course in the field of translation and it is a continuation of the "Reading Translation I" course in the previous term. In this context, it is seen that there is no difference and diversity in terms of translation courses in the first and second semesters at KKKU. It is noteworthy that general language skills courses in KKKU continue in this period as a continuation of the first term.

Table 6: 3rd Semester Field Information Course Distribution

No	Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University	Kırıkkale University	Karamanoglu Mehmetbey University
1.	Post-Islamic Arab Culture II	Arabic Grammar III	Applied Grammar I
2.	News Translation II (Turkish-Arabic)	Arabic Text Translation I	Text Analysis for Translation I
3.	Translation Theories	Oral Expression I	Oral Communication III
4.	Arabic Modern Texts	Turkish-Arabic Translation I	Turkish to Arabic Translation I
5.	Oral Expression III	Written Expression II	Written Expression III
6.	Literary Translation I	Arabic Literature (Classical Period) I	Translation Theories and Methods I
7.	Legal Translation III (Arabic-Turkish)	-	-
8.	Complex Language Structures I (Prepositions and Conjunctions)	-	-

When the courses in the third semester of the Arabic Translation and Interpreting program are examined, it is noteworthy that there are language skills courses in each program. In addition, it is seen that the programs in KKKU and KKKU contain courses closer to each other. Besides, while there are grammar, oral and written expression lessons in KKKU and KKKU programs, AYBU has only oral expression courses in this semester similarly. In addition to the high number of courses of AYBU, lessons on special field translations draw attention. It is striking that the special field translation courses available in the third semester of the program at this university are not included in the other two programs. Instead that, both programs include more general translation courses. It can be commented that there is an intensive translation training at AYBU in this semester. In addition, while it is seen that courses on translation theories take place in AYBU and KKKU, it is seen that a similar course is not included in the program during the education at KKKU.

Table 7: 4th Semester Field Information Course Distribution

No	Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University	Kırıkkale University	Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey University
1.	Post-Islamic Arab Culture III	Arabic Grammar IV	Applied Grammar II
2.	News Translation III (Arabic-Turkish)	Arabic Text Translation II	Text Analysis for Translation II
3.	Consecutive Interpreting	Oral Expression II	Verbal Communication IV
4.	Classical Arabic Texts	Translation from Turkish into Arabic II	Translation from Turkish into Arabic II
5.	Oral Expression IV	Written Expression III	Written Expression IV
6.	Literary Translation II	Arabic Literature (Modern Period) II (Elective)	Translation Theory and Methods II
7.	Legal Translation IV (Turkish-Arabic)	-	-
8.	Complex Language Structures II (Phrases)	-	-
9.	Note Taking Techniques	-	-

When the table is examined, it is seen that there are courses in the programs of each 3 departments as a continuation of the 3rd semester. It is noteworthy that the number of courses in AYBU program has increased in this semester. In the other two programs, as a continuation of the 3rd semester, there was no change in the number of courses. Also in this period, the density of the lessons for special field translation in AYBU's program is observed. In addition, it should be noted that the "Consecutive Translation" course, which is one of the oral translation types, is only included in AYBU's program in this period.

Table 8: 5th Semester Field Information Course Distribution

No	Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University	Kırıkkale University	Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey University
1.	Consecutive Translation II (Turkish-Arabic)	Oral Translation Techniques	Consecutive Translation I
2.	Simultaneous Translation I (Arabic-Turkish)	Simultaneous Translation I	Advanced Arabic I
3.	Literary Translation III	Written Translation Techniques I	Written Translation Techniques
4.	Tourism Translation I	Expert Texts I	Special Field Translation I (Press)
5.	Effective Communication Skills I	Dialects of Arabic	Dialects of Arabic I
6.	Diplomacy Translation	Grammar Analysis I	Arab Cultural History I
7.	Legal Translation V	-	Translation History I
8.	Technical Translation I	-	

When the courses in the 5th semester of the Arabic Translation and Interpreting program are examined, it is seen that three programs focus on both oral and written translation courses in this semester. Compared to the other two departments, AYBU has more courses and translation courses for special purposes. In addition to translation courses, there is Effective Communication Skills course at AYBU, Grammar Analysis course at KKU and Advanced Arabic courses in Translation History and Arab Cultural History at KMU. There are special purpose translation courses in five different fields in the 5th semester of the program at AYBU. In this context, only Specialization Texts are available at KKU. In KMU, there is only Special Field Translation (Press) course.

Table 9: 6th Semester Field Information Course Distribution

No	Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University	Kırıkkale University	Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey University
1.	Consecutive Translation III	Oral Translation Techniques II	Consecutive Translation II
2.	Simultaneous Translation II (Arabic-Turkish)	Simultaneous Translation II	Translation History II
3.	Effective Communication Skills II	Dialects of Arabic II	Dialects of Arabic II
4.	Tourism Translation II	Expert Texts II	Special Field Translation II (Trade and Economics)
5.	Technical Translation II	Grammar Analysis II	Advanced Arabic II
6.	Religious Texts Terminology and Translation I	Written Translation Techniques II	Written Translation Techniques II
7.	Medical Translation I	-	Arab Cultural History II
8.	Arabic Proverbs and Idioms	-	-

When the courses in the 6th semester of the Arabic Translation and Interpreting programs are examined, it is seen that the 6th semester lessons are the continuation of the 5th semester lessons. However, some courses differ between departments. These different courses are Religious Texts Terminology and Translation, Medical Translation and Arabic Proverbs and Idioms at AYBU, and Special Field Translation (Business and Economics) at KMU. In KKU, it can be said that the courses in this semester are the continuation of the courses in the 5th semester.

Table 10: 7th Semester Field Information Course Distribution

No	Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University	Kırıkkale University	Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey University
1.	Internship	Simultaneous Translation III	Simultaneous Translation I
2.	Religious Texts Terminology and Translation II	Arabic Written and Visual Media I	Discourse Translation (Ar-Tr)
3.	Medical Translation II	Media Translation I	Community Translation
4.	Scientific Research Methods	Scientific Texts I	Linguistics
5.	Basic Sources of Arabic	Special Topics I	Translation of Special Fields III (Academic Texts)
6.	Dialects of Arabic I	Dialects of Arabic III	Research Techniques in Social Sciences
7.	Language Proficiency Assessment Techniques	-	-
8.	Computerized Translation Technologies	-	-

When the 7th semester courses of Arabic Translation and Interpretation departments are examined, it is seen that most of the courses of all three universities consist of translation courses. Among the AYBU courses, there is an "internship" course as applied. In addition, as special subject courses in translation, "Religious Texts Terminology and Translation II," "Medical Translation II" and "Computerized Translation Technologies"; Among the KKU courses are Media "Translation I"; Among the courses of KMU, there are "Discourse Translation (Ar-Tr)," "Community Translation" and Special Field Translation III (Academic Texts). " AYBU is seen to be more comprehensive in terms of special field translation lessons.

Table 11: 8th Semester Field Information Course Distribution

No	Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University	Kırıkkale University	Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey University
1.	Final project	Simultaneous Translation IV	Simultaneous Translation II
2.	Dialects of Arabic II	Dialects of Arabic IV	Discourse Translation II (Tr-Ar)
3.	Digital Media Translation	Media Translation II	Special Field Translation IV (Subtitle-Dubbing)
4.	Translation Applications	Scientific Texts II	Computer Aided Translation
5.	Contemporary Arab World	Arabic Written and Visual Media II	Linguistics II
6.	Arabic Manuscript Review	Special Topics II	Thesis

When the 8th semester courses of Arabic Translation and Interpretation programs are examined, it is seen that the number of last term courses is 6 in all three programs, and it is seen that all three universities concentrate on translation special field courses in this period. Among AYBU courses, there are "Digital Media Translation," "Translation Practice" courses as special field courses; Among the KKU courses, "Simultaneous Translation IV," "Media Translation" courses, and among KMU courses, "Simultaneous Translation II," "Discourse Translation II (Tr-Ar)," Special Field Translation IV (Subtitle-Dubbing) and "Computer Aided It is seen that there are "translation" lessons. It is seen that especially KKU "Simultaneous Translation" and "Dialects of Arabic" courses consist of four semesters. In addition, KMU "Special Field Translation" courses consist of four semesters and each semester focuses on a different translation area. It is noteworthy that the last semester "Graduation Project" and "Graduation Thesis" courses are included in AYBU and KMU programs. When the three programs are examined, it is seen that the courses in the field of translation are more in the KMU program.

4. Conclusion and Suggestions

In this research, Arabic Translation and Interpretation departments in our country undergraduate education programs; The number of courses, course distribution, the ratio of translation courses to other courses and course contents were evaluated. In the school-based curriculum development approach, it is emphasized that education programs are developed as a result of planning, design, implementation and evaluation studies carried out by institutions (Skilbeck, 1984). Based on this, when the Arabic Translation and Interpreting undergraduate programs are examined, the existing undergraduate programs have been examined in order to reveal whether the program development stages have been carried out and to reveal a more effective program.

Since the Arabic Translation and Interpreting departments in Turkey are still new departments, the undergraduate education programs of the first three universities that started education were discussed. It is possible to summarize the results obtained as follows. When the number of courses and courses of Arabic translation and interpretation departments of all three universities are examined, it is noteworthy that the current department at Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University has an intense program content compared to the two departments in other universities. In addition, it can be said that AYBU offers its students the opportunity to meet with the translation sector with the internship course in the 4th semester, which is not included in the other two departments. When the undergraduate programs of Arabic Translation and Interpretation departments were examined in terms of the number of courses, it was found that 71 courses in Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University, 56 courses in Kırıkkale University and 54 courses in Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey University were included in the programs of the departments. According to the data, it is noteworthy that translation field courses are more intense in AYBU than KMU and KKKU courses. However, when the ratio of translation courses to other courses within departments is examined, the ratio of translation courses is 40.2% in AYBU, 37.1% in KKKU and 41.6% in KMU. Based on this, it was noted that KKKU's undergraduate program was less than the other two universities in terms of the number of translation courses.

At the end of the study, it was concluded that a common curriculum should be prepared that will contribute to the development of students and eliminate the differences between departments by determining the negative and positive aspects of the curriculum. In this context, the following suggestions that will contribute to the development of students and departments in Translation and Interpretation departments can be considered:

- A commission should be established to examine the curricula of Arabic Translation and Interpretation departments and to prepare a common curriculum,
- In the preparation of the curriculum, the intensity of translation courses should be taken into account,
- Translation course diversity should be determined,
- Which of the special purpose translation courses should be included, should be determined,
- Weekly class hour intensity should be determined,
- The number of courses to be taken per semester should be determined,
- The intensity of the culture lessons should be determined,
- The intensity of the application courses should be determined,
- The current number of faculty members should be taken into consideration while preparing the curriculum,
- Students must have knowledge in the field of translation by working in various public and private institutions at certain intervals in the years before graduation,
- Faculty members from different universities in these departments should come together in a workshop organized for curriculum study and evaluate all aspects of the curriculum,
- If possible, it should be evaluated by taking suggestions that will contribute to the development of the program from the students who graduated from this undergraduate program from different universities and work in the field of translation,
- An intensive study should be done by bringing together translation experts in various fields, at least once in each semester, in a one-day workshop with students,
- With the changes in the field of translation, technological developments and the translation sector should be followed up by the academic community and updated in the curriculum of the departments when necessary,
- Developments in translation technology should be followed by field experts, students should be informed about this and students should be encouraged in studies that can be done in this field.

It is a known fact that it is impossible to make a translation with only theoretical knowledge. Although universities include theoretical and practical courses in their curriculum, it is thought that internships in the sector and meeting with experts who translate in various fields in different activities will contribute to their development. Translator candidates who come together with translation experts in various fields will focus on improving themselves by realizing what difficulties are encountered in the field of practice. In these programs, necessary arrangements can be made in order for the existing curricula to allow this.

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